

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Date: 14th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxxxxx since 2014. xxxxxxxx human resources and any xxxxxx related to VMMC. xxxxxxin HIV activities.

What is your understanding of sustainability of VMMC?

This is where VMMC services are offered uninterrupted and without so much dependence on donors.

What are decisions might be taking place in the future state where EIMC and EAMC are sustainable and integrated?

Policy: There is need for strong policy to be in place on sustainability and integration of EIMC and EAMC. Currently, there is no policy for EIMC and EAMC.

Service Delivery: More health facilities should be offering EIMC and EAMC in the future state. Currently, EIMC and EAMC is being monitored but without targets.

Training: EIMC and EAMC should be incorporated in pre-service training in colleges offering health and medical studies. In addition, further trainings may need to be conducted alongside competence follow-ups.

Who might be involved in making decisions around policy/service delivery/training ?

Policy: Health promotion unit may be involved. Data will be coming from registers. EIMC is necessary especially that about 2 million people have been circumcised. If we have to be sustainable, then we target infants and adolescents.

Who do they report to? It can be both Government and donors. Government should initiate the policy development process. Do you think the implementation partners are pushing this? Implementation partners bring Government agenda.

Service Delivery: Community, all health care workers and National Health Authority should be involved in making decisions around EIMC.

What might be barriers around service delivery decision-making? Every concept comes with challenges. It may be acceptance issues especially among those who believe that babies should not be circumcised.

Training: Engagement with professional bodies such as General Nursing Council (GNC), Health Professional Council of Zambia (HPCZ), Zambia Medical Association (ZMA) and Clinical Officers Association of Zambia (COAZ).

What might be the barriers around training decision-making? This should not be difficult. Government would need to explain and incorporate training of EIMC under the policy.

Assuming that Government policy exists, what might be the process look like? Government says EIMC should be integrated. In terms of the process,

- a) It is the district's mandate to communicate to the health facility about the policy change.
- b) Assessing and identifying which health care workers will play a key role. Is it In-Charge, nurses etc.?
- c) They will come up with challenges on human resources and infrastructure. Space is an issue in health facilities. That is why integration is the way to go.

How might the process be on training decision-making? Technical Working Group (TWG) might be better placed to push the agenda. At district level, the VMMC coordinator spreads it to the sub-district focal point person.

What type of decisions might you be influencing? Routinization. In the context of EIMC/EAMC, decisions would need to be made in terms of which health facilities will need to implement EIMC and EAMC and also decisions around consumables.

In a sustainable and future state, how do you hope management of trainings can be done?

If the district is in-charge, on-site trainings would be good since they are less expensive. Resources can be an impediment. Also, attrition of trained personnel.

If VMMC activities are integrated in Maternal Child Health (MCH) department, do you anticipate any challenges?

- a) Work overload from workers.
- b) Getting involvement of MCH may have some resistance.

- c) Need for specific human resources for counseling.
- d) Cognitive bandwidth is an issue

With the ART programme, there were a lot of re-arranging and workflow challenges.

What might be the process to deal with the resistance?

- a) Continuous engagement and emphasizing that VMMC is important and should be integrated.
- b) Make a duty time-table or roster for health care workers.

What is the motivation for the health facilities?

- a) Reduction of HIV transmissions. Health care providers are trained at a cost and should be able to offer a service.
- b) We have medical kit for each health facility. Under planning, we have VMMC included and if they don't do it, it will make it look bad. Moving forward it will be easier. With new tools, VMMC can be monitored and assessed for EIMC and EAMC.

Is there a focal point person at the health facility? There is a VMMC focal point person at sub-district level as well as at health facility level.

Any thoughts on Supply Chain?

With the district central pharmacy, we had a bad experience where VMMC consumables were used for other things. The current supply chain is the best and still needs to be improved on. VMMC prefers a system where supplies are recorded at the district. But if storage was not an issue, then storage by the district would be good and where need arises, consumables can be used. Environment Health Technician (EHT) have had problems with the centralized storage system.

Prioritization is not well-managed right now. What would be the process of prioritization? It maybe a question of adding VMMC requisites to the essential kits.

Do you do in inter-departmental forecasting for respectively? I think so. And shortages are due to non – supply. Not everything is delivered.

Assuming next year there was no JHPIEGO and CIDRZ and other partners. What are the top 5 areas that you might focus on?

Supply Chain would need to be fixed. Ministry of Health would need to put human resources and infrastructure in place.

Do you imagine VMMC without allowances? It can stand but we would need to engagement.

What might be your motivation towards routinization of VMMC condition? We are already doing it. We would need to ensure that they are practicing what they were trained in.

What motivates health care providers to do the work of VMMC?

- a) It is part of the job description
- b) Passion to work with or without money.
- c) Fear of not being recommended to attend a workshop.

What is motivates you to move towards sustainability of VMMC?

- a) Desire to contribute to HIV eradication.
- b) Promotion is one of them especially when I do quality work.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxx Health Office, xxxxxx, xxxxx of Health

Date: 15th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

VMMC goes hand in hand with social mobilisation. As health promotions unit, we use vehicles and front-line staff to disseminate the right information using fliers and IECs materials. When funds are available, we make use of the radio.

xxxxxxx. Identification of sites, procurement of commodities and training of providers were some of the key roles. Also, general supervision and ensuring that staff are doing their job. xxxxxxxx. In this process, we would involve all implementing partners and district staff. We also used to have meetings to review campaigns and performance.

What does sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

Sustainability means that the whole VMMC programme or activities become solely funded by the Ministry of Health.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where EIMC/EAMC are integrated?

Policy: Need for creation of position for VMMC provider.

What might the decision process look like for establishing new providers for VMMC? What are some of the decisions that may need to be made at your level?

- a) **There will be a supervision line established.** Decisions will have to be made to see where the VMMC unit will be domiciled. Is it under public health or clinical care department of Ministry of Health? Provincial Health Director will then assign the matter to Public Health or Clinical Care Director.
- b) **Public Health or Clinical Care directorate will then need to identify space and sites.**

What might be some motivations for creating the VMMC provider/unit? The motivation is that we are moving towards epidemic control of HIV. This can be done in collaboration with National HIV Unit xxxxxxxxxx xxxxxx. The developed strategies will help to achieve HIV epidemic control with the implementation of VMMC.

What might be some barriers around creating the VMMC provider/unit? It is sustained provision of commodities. In terms of decision-making, I don't see any barriers provided that the policy on EIMC and EAMC is in place.

What might the decision process look like for identification of space for VMMC unit? It will be a directive which needs to be executed.

What might be some barriers around identification of space?

- a) **Finding the right people.** Public Health Unit would have to rely on someone to it. In terms of finding the right people, will it be a nurse or a medical doctor? We often lack the human resources capacity.
- b) **There will be a lot of work in managing the de-learning of incentives.** This can easily be resolved by the use of performance appraisals process in which staff performance is evaluated against the set targets.

Assuming VMMC is integrated in the workplans, what might the process be?

- a) Provincial Health Director will inform the Public Health Unit that each district should have 10 active VMMC sites.

- b) District Officers will lead this process and implement, and it becomes part of the workplan.
- c) In terms of measuring performance, the public health unit will develop an action plan with annual deliverables. Based on this, staff will develop their workplans and this will be part of the planning process.

What is the planning process like? Planning process begins in June and 3 year work plans are developed. Different departments submit work plans by end of October. Usually, individual work plans are submitted to head of units. The targets are reviewed every quarter. From health facility level, In-charge would submit to the district and then province and finally national level. At every level, the workplans and budget need to be consolidated.

Funding: VMMC will need to be budgeted for.

Service delivery: Need for a specific VMMC unit to be created. Currently, we have no VMMC providers and nurses are usually used. Also, implementation partners have employed some staff to coordinate VMMC activities. Social mobilisation and demand creation are happening.

Currently, service delivery is okay. If we focus on infants and adolescents, does it change? It has to change because the focus will then be the care-givers. In terms of the existing process, we will need to

- a) Develop new strategies
- b) Develop materials
- c) Conduct orientation of staff to the new strategies and materials.

Supply Chain: VMMC commodities will need to be part of the essential medicines kit. Most of the VMMC commodities are bought by partners. From the health facility, the order is made in the electronic logistics management system (ELMIS). The order or request from health facility is sent to Medical Stores Limited (MSL) and then the stock is packed. However, we incorporate VMMC, the ELMIS will need to be updated and coded.

In terms of the process, there must be agreement that we will incorporate VMMC to be part of the essential medicines kit. This process will be led at National level by the Head of Pharmacy Unit and MSL.

What barriers might be experienced with supply chain? Staff will need to learn the system in terms of how to request or order the commodities.

Any other insights around indicators, routinization and cross-ministry collaboration?
Routinization of VMMC services, supply chain, space or infrastructure and support

equipment are key and these would need to be made available. Its important that health promotions is strengthened in order to create demand.

Indicators

MoH is always tracking VMMC indicators so as to assess performance.

Cross-Ministry Collaboration

I have not seen much of this. The challenges have to do with availability of funds.

Imagine the VMMC programme without partners? Currently, we would fail to meet our targets. Sites that are performing well is due to the help from implementing partners. The implementing partners have employed social mobilisers.

What decisions might need to be made?

- a) Put in place VMMC provider. Director Human Resources and Permanent Secretary (PS) should submit to Public Service Management Division (PSMD) for creation and funding of the position of VMMC Coordinator. Authority needs to come from PS so that when the district also makes decisions, the decisions are supported by the PS.
- b) Identify the space
- c) Need for supply chain

In terms of removal of incentives, Provincial Health Director will have to write to PS Ministry of Health and the decision will be to implement VMMC activities without incentives. Incentives are bad for sustainability.

However, incentives help in meeting targets. At provincial level, supervising officers would have to ensure that the MoH goals or legacy goals are met.

Training

Training of health providers in infant and adolescent male circumcision is key.

What training model or package would be for health providers? It would be one that requires suitable human resources like anesthetists. Sites would need to have theatre settings. We also need to take advantage of training institutions and design a course i.e. pre-service training. But sometimes, its limited in the way it was done. A dedicated training would need to be done. This should be incorporated during the planning cycle.

xxxxxx not use midwives for EIMC due to the shortage of that cadre of staff.

What is your personal motivation to move towards sustainable VMMC? At the end of the day, xxxxxx legacy that xxxx here and contributed to the process. Give me a task and I will do it to the best and be documented that I was part of the process.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxx

Date: 13th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxxx. He is involved in xxxxxxxxx.

What is your understanding of sustainability of VMMC?

It is about MoH taking up all the activities that are donor-led.

What are decisions that that might be taking place in the future state where EIMC and EAMC are sustainable and integrated?

Policy: Guidelines on EIMC would need to be in place and disseminated at different levels. Routinization of the service is key. EIMC and EAMC should be part of the essential medicines (or kit). However, in terms of implementation, it is a different ball game all together. In the transitional state, development of EIMC materials and engaging the General Nursing Council (GNC) is key. But EIMC and EAMC are perceived to be additional work.

Who might be involved in making decisions around policy? At MoH national level, it is important to interrogate how EIMC would be implemented. What is the role of training institutions? All people coming out of training institutions should be incorporated into the programme.

What might be some of the barriers in making decisions around policy?

- a) Adoption of policy is okay but then the issue would be on implementation. MoH may need to develop a policy on prioritization of resources.
- b) GNC: We need to ensure that GNC is brought on board. If there was any litigation, MoH at national level would engage GNC.
- c) Infrastructure: Health Professional Council of Zambia (HPCZ) has prescribed standards of how the theatre for male circumcision should be and should have.

Funding: Donor funding would cease and MoH will take a leading role in funding VMMC activities. Services would need to be routinised. Involvement of local communities such as business entities and churches may also be key in resource mobilisation. In the transitional state, funding for EAMC is poor. Mobilisation of community members to provide resources for VMMC program is key. This was done in Southern province where business houses, churches and individuals made some contributions.

The activities for VMMC need to be part of the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF). The planning cycle under Ministry of Health should be applied in which health facilities develop workplans and budgets which are consolidated at district level and sent to the province for further consolidation and quality assurance and finally submitted to MoH at national level. There is also need for indicative figures or ceilings for planning purposes. This would reduce the back and forth processes during planning and budgeting.

Service delivery: Routinization of services for EIMC. Nurses would need to be capacity built to conduct male circumcision surgery. EIMC to be coordinated by midwives and to be part of Maternal Child Health department. Male circumcision to be conducted to infants between the age of 6 and 9 months. In the transitional state, the main challenge is limited space in most health facilities.

VMMC services should be routinised and there should be no expectation of payment/allowances. EIMC and EAMC should run without allowances just like the way OPD and ART operate.

Training: EIMC should be part of pre-service course for health care providers. This would call for revision of the curriculum and building the capacity of the current tutors and training. Logistics management would need to be included in the curriculum as the current focus is mainly on how to care for patients.

Assuming that EIMC and EAMC policy is in place and we are at a point of curriculum development, the following can be done:

- a) Bring together the key experts to transfer knowledge
- b) Hold workshops to ensure modifications to the curriculum. This would involve key players like implementation partners, surgical society, GNC etc.
- c) Training institutions would need to be provided with the required and necessary materials for training purposes such as models.
- d) Training of health care providers on standards.

The potential barriers would be that private schools would need to buy these themselves. And Government may not be able to adequately fund the training institutions.

Supply Chain: Assuming that implementation partners are out of the picture. Drug kits have to be bought centrally under the supervision and coordination of Medical Stores Limited of Zambia (MSL). In the transitional state, there is bottom-up planning. Supply chain is guided by the targets set and MSL has a schedule of deliveries to different health facilities.

The potential barriers under supply chain would be as follows:

- a) Forecasting by MSL tends to be poor and this would negatively impact the VMMC program. Also, the delivery schedule by MSL is not in line with the needs of the health facilities.
- b) Most health care providers are clinical people with little knowledge on logistics management. Need for capacity building.
- c) Clearance of procured drugs would need to be obtained from ZAMRA. MoH would procure centrally and MSL would handle the deliveries.

What would be Government's motivation for sustainable VMMC? VMMC is seen as a preventative program for HIV infections. Motivation will be the impact of the VMMC modelling. If we continue on this path, then there will be a reduction in expenditure. For VMMC, the impact start to be seen in 2020 and 2030. The planning cycle should be moved to long term.

What would be the donor's motivation for sustainable VMMC? We can learn lessons from the ART program which does not experience stock-outs. Currently, implementation partners (CIDRZ, JPHIEGO, CHAZ etc) procure commodities from different sources and suppliers. However, when commodities are procured centrally, quality standards are guaranteed and there is an opportunity for negotiated prices due to bulk purchases.

Closing Remarks

What motivates you to move towards sustainability?

- a) If VMMC becomes sustainable, services will become accessible. And it is not all health facilities that will have VMMC services.
- b) Staff will be on payroll and there will be no nagging about allowances.

Who should be making decisions? It has to come from MoH. Policy pronouncement will come from the Minister. Then a circular which is signed on any issue and the staff will be expected to follow. Technical Working Group (TWG) is part of the decision-making process and collaborate with permanent Secretary of MoH. In this regard, even the agenda for sustainable VMMC will need to come from TWG. TWG needs to be setting the goal and also measure the impact.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Date: 14th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxxxx the Adverse Events (AEs) as compared to VMMC. xxxxxxxx the management of VMMC at xxxxxx level.

What does sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

It means management of the VMMC programme independent of implementation partners (IPs) and also finding ways of scaling up the programme. So when CIDRZ is not available, we should still be able to provide quality health service. Then, I would say that we are sustainable.

Are there any differences in terms of targets?

PEPFAR is interested in clients who above 10. My role is to ensure AEs are attended to. EIMC protects against penal cancer and it is beneficial if circumcision is done before the age of 10. So, if a service can protect against cancer, then Ministry of Health (MoH) should have a strong support for it.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where EIMC/EAMC are integrated?

Policy: Some clear directive regarding the age for circumcision. Also, it is important to generate evidence that meets our local needs. Primary input can be obtained from urologists and other practitioners.

Who is involved in making policy decisions? It needs to start from Policy at Ministry of Health (MoH) Headquarters. On VMMC, nothing much has been done. At MoH, the policy document should be given to experts. It is the duty of MoH to reach out to the local experts. Sustainability has to do with local ownership and collaboration. MoH should be in the driving seat.

What kind of policy do you think you might want to make? It must be a policy that is all inclusive and that addresses key issues. There must also be a consultative process. For instance, surgeons are key and they need to be consulted.

What policy decisions would you make towards sustainability of VMMC? xxxxxxxx sub-district coordinators. It should not be based on individuals. Also, safety and quality should be considered.

What might be some barriers on Policy? Bureaucracy is the main barrier. For decisions to move from district to Permanent Secretary level, it takes long. Policy makers tend to be busy with other tasks.

Funding: Funding should be consistent and IPs to be funding provinces. And it will be good to learn lessons.

Do you think there is a part for health facility and sub-district level to contribute to funding? Most of the funds are at the level of administration and this is where partners have been funding supplies for VMMC.

Given available funds at district level, how do you make decisions around sustainability? Unfortunately, with limited funds, VMMC may not get anything and this is on the premise that Global Fund and CDC have pulled out support.

How do you see VMMC in terms of Partner Support? Sustainability is not merely about talking but availability of funds.

Assuming that CDC, CIDRZ and other partners are out of the picture, what decisions might you make for the VMMC programme to be sustainable?

- a) Ensure that VMMC is enshrined in policy documents
- b) xxxxx, xxxxx to ensure dedicated space and personnel and supply and also integrate VMMC talks during outreach at district levels.

c) Need to offer quality service to the people.

Sustainability is not just about money but about administrative skills and partners would need to work with district staff so as to enhance sustainability.

Service Delivery: VMMC should be integrated to be part of the health facilities. Currently, in some health facilities, some health care workers are focusing on the VMMC programme and reporting of the targets.

There is need for some policy directives on the creation of VMMC coordinator position to be part of the civil service. This would need to be moved by the Public Service Management Division and Ministry of Health. The organizational structure on how the VMMC coordinator is working should be clear.

Integration of VMMC with other services is key especially with the shortage of manpower in health facilities.

Do you think midwives are best suited to coordinate VMMC activities in sustainable future? No. VMMC should stop riding on other cadre of staff. The solution lies in having a dedicated cadre, VMMC Coordinator.

What might be some barriers on service delivery in the future state? Shortage of personnel at health facility level, bureaucracy and transportation challenges for outreach programmes.

Training: VMMC should not just focus on certification. VMMC should be integrated in the training of clinical officers, medical officers, nurses and other health care workers. The training should not just focus on the surgery but on administration of VMMC. There should also be mentorship programme on a daily basis.

Supply Chain: VMMC should be part of the national supply chain managed by the Medical Stores Limited.

Indicators: There is need for clinical indicators which can inform public health indicators.

Cross-Ministry Collaboration: VMMC programme can collaborate with Ministry of Information, Defense Forces and Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs. Currently, the Ministry of Health has been collaborating well with other line ministries especially during the Cholera epidemic.

How do you hope to achieve the strategies around sustainability of VMMC? To assume that the district staff will translate the strategies and policies requires for testing their knowledge through performance appraisals. We need to provide services in order to yield sustainability. And it is important that people are allowed to operate within their

sphere of speciality. In this case, urologists need to be involved. There is also need to address the needs of health providers by engaging them in a participatory process. Also, the district coordinators and managers need to be part of the VMMC trainings.

What is your personal motivation for VMMC?

- a) Patients accessing quality service. Quality and service comes first for me.
- b) Sustainability also means providing clarity on the roles of the different stakeholders. There is need to engage implementation partners and Health Professions Council of Zambia is key for sustainability of the programme.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Date: 13th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

He has been taking xxxxxx District. However, he also plays a role xxxxx xxxxxxxx VMMC.

What is your understanding of sustainability of VMMC?

In my view, this is where we take the VMMC programme to be solely handled by the government and easily taken up by the health facilities

What are decisions that that might be taking place in the future state where EIMC and EAMC are sustainable and integrated?

Policy: We have the 2016 – 2020 policy document that outlines issues of sustainability and integration of EIMC and EAMC. However, in the transitional state, the sustainability road map was signed and EIMC and EAMC will be the focus.

Who might be involved in making decisions around policy? It is the Permanent Secretary (PS) at MoH who can call for a meeting with donors/funders. The PS, who is the controlling officer, is mandated to call for a meeting. Decisions will need to be concretized at that high level. Based on the evaluation of VMMC which was undertaken, the PS can present the findings to implementing partners. Technical Working Group can make some recommendations.

Funding: Funding for EIMC is key. Global fund would need to supplement on the resources together with Government and Implementation partners. However, in terms of the transitional state, implementation of EIMC is at zero. EIMC was incorporated in the trainings organized by Global Fund. EAMC has funding and EIMC will also need funding.

Evaluation of VMMC was conducted in 2018. There are some key steps that may need to be undertaken. And CHAI may have some information. It may be good to look at the targets that we want to achieve and budget around that. Also, we can see what funds can be made available by Government and lobby for funds from implementing partners.

What are some of the barriers around funding decision-making?

- a) EIMC has not kicked off due to the focus of the present funding. The focus is mainly on reducing HIV infections among the 15 – 29 years. In that case, the long-term goal may not be realized.
- b) Global Fund was not engaged. In the 2017 – 2020 application the intention was for staff to be trained in EIMC. However, Dr. xxxx and xxxx may know the final decision made in the application.
- c) Traditional issues can be barriers. But these are better handled through collaboration with the Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs. Traditionally, the focus of VMMC is on adolescents.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis being made here is that funding should be embedded in workplans at different levels, including at district. VMMC should be planned for. Also, the hypothesis is that implementation partners will provide adequate funding.

Service delivery: There is need to have adequate staffing levels in health facilities. The target is such that by 2020, district hospitals to provide EIMC in demand basis. However,

in terms of the transitional state, the available resources used for adult circumcision can still be applied for EAMC and it is quite different with EIMC. CIDRZ launched the EIMC training manual.

Training: Training of health staff in EIMC in district hospitals and health facilities with maternity services. The midwives would be a target. In terms of the transitional state, there are few trained staff in the health facilities.

Supply Chain: There would be need for supplies for EIMC. The centralized managed supply chain system is key. Similarly, the same way the HIV tests are managed. Partners can buy and such resources can then be pushed in one basket. In terms of the transitional state, EAMC is already happening. But supply chain is the weakest part of the VMMC program. Currently, there is no central basket for supplies.

Indicators: We may need to focus on indicators related to EIMC. There would be need to also involve monitoring and evaluation (M&E) team. An indicator like 'proportion of babies born and circumcised in the first 2 months' and also 'adverse events' would be good. However, in the transitional state, the indicators of 0 to 2 months are contained in HMIS.

Cross-Ministry Collaboration: EIMC would focus on Ministry of Education (MoE) and Ministry of Traditional Affairs. But also, there would also be room for to collaborate with Members of Parliament (MPs) and other stakeholders. In the transitional state, there is collaboration between MoH and MoE and Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs and such collaboration would need to be enhanced.

Is the VMMC program doing enough to capture the out-of-school? Yes – there is something being done (but no statistics). Traditional leaders have been engaged. A study to assess the impact of traditional engagement. However, with EIMC, it may be slightly different.

Closing Remarks

What motivates you to move towards sustainability? VMMC is doing well as seen by the statistics and also in preventing HIV infections as shown by the evaluations study which was conducted. When I look at that, this is a good one-time procedure that helps to prevent HIV. If VMMC could be part of routine service, then we will save funds.

What are your greatest barriers? Training is the main issue. Most health facilities do not have adequate health staff. I know xxxx is doing well in VMMC with limited number of health providers and health facilities. Again, this hinders on funding.

What can account for the success of Kafue district? It is closer to Lusaka and the district has a good partner, that is, Medical Stores Limited for supplies.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Date: 12th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxx xxxxxxx

What are your general thoughts on sustainability of VMMC?

Current situation is not organized. There is donor fatigue. VMMC is the only programme where health providers are paid allowances during delivery of routine health service.

What would you say about the future outlook for VMMC?

It is important for Ministry of Health (MoH) to set the agenda for VMMC.

Can you talk to me about the decisions around policy in the future state?

There is need for clear policy on EIMC

Trainings in the future state

There is need for training for EIMC and EAMC. Trainings should begin from Colleges that train nurses. And this may call for collaboration with Ministry of Education.

Supply Chain in the future state

Supplies should be provided at national level by MoH. You don't expect implementation partners to provide supplies for VMMC. MoH should be in the forefront of providing supplies for VMMC just like it is done for TB and ART programme.

Funding in the future state

MoH should provide a budget for VMMC to the national treasury.

Service delivery in the future state

Service delivery should become routine.

Indicators in the future state

Indicators for VMMC should be similar for ART and should be drawn from the national database for VMMC.

What are some of the decisions happening or exemplifying sustainable EIMC and EAMC?

Decisions will be made at MoH national level. MoH should set the agenda and all players should be able to support such actions.

What decisions are happening at a policy level?

There is need for coordination from MoH so that the VMMC agenda is driven. Currently, the VMMC coordination is happening at the level of program officers. MoH needs to have more authority.

There is need for more ownership of EAMC. Money is paid to health care providers for service delivery.

What decisions are happening with regards to funding?

Decisions should be made from MoH. EIMC and EAMC should be part of the national budget.

Are there any transitional decisions that need to happen before EIMC and EAMC is sustainable?

Service delivery: A regulatory body for quality at health facility level is key. Quality standards should be set by institutions like the Health Professionals Council of Zambia (HPCZ). If a health facility does not meet the quality standards set by HPCZ, then VMMC services should not be provided.

Training: Training for VMMC should be incorporated into training of nurses. Practicing licenses should be standard. If there are new technologies, these should be introduced at college level.

Supply Chain: At the moment, it is the implementation partners who buy supplies for VMMC. When MoH took over, there are no supplies. Ideally, the supplies should be

available at national level. Each of the implementing partners were either buying supplies locally or even importing. Since it's a national service, it should be linked into the national supply chain which is the Medical Store Limited (MSL).

What are the top decisions in the future stage? Policy, funding, service delivery and supply chain. At the same time, indicators and cross-ministry collaboration are also key in creating demand for VMMC.

Who should be involved in making decisions in the future state and what are some of the dynamics? MoH and donors. There has been a lot of work done in VMMC including research and some things have not been implemented. Donors have been frustrated after spending too much money. MoH will need to set the agenda in coordinating VMMC activities. At the same time, having an accountable person at MoH would be motivating to donors. Therefore, policy is key for the future of EIMC and EAMC.

What are some of barriers that donors may have?

Provision of incentives in the form of lunch allowance to health service providers has negatively affected the VMMC programme. It is therefore important to begin to move towards ownership.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxxx

Date: 12th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxxx

What are some of the decisions happening in each of the categories in the future state?

Policy: VMMC campaigns have been funded and this shows that there is political will. There is also support from traditional leaders. Right now, people are trained during the VMMC campaigns and there are a lot of numbers realized from such activities. When VMMC started, there were incentives provided. To come out of this trap, we tried to make VMMC routine. We tried to sustain campaigns without incentives and the results

were bad. VMMC is just like any other service and should be integrated into health delivery service.

Funding: We get funds from MoH, CDC and Global Fund. These funds come with targets and conditions. Each provincial coordinator is paid by CDC. In the future, there should be a way of MoH pooling a lot of resources to generate sustainability. There is need to have accountability checks. Where does accountability lie? Integrated type of service is difficult to maintain quality. Going forward, we want MoH to push for provision of routine health services.

What are some of the decisions that may need to be made in terms of funding? We need sustained funding. It is better to conduct a research to highlight the impact of VMMC. Who would be involved in such decisions? MoH

Service delivery: The challenge is space in the health facilities especially when we try to integrate. VMMC is not an emergence. We use the same space for the other routine health services. Mobile VMMC works more than static as seen from the results. So, we must invest more in mobile outreach. There is need for more prefabs and materials needed for VMMC. Outreach has proved to be more reliable. My future is in outreach or mobile VMMC.

Are there any transitional decisions that you make to support service delivery? We are buying commodities, emergency trays etc. Resource allocation should shift to outreach or mobile VMMC.

Training: We would like to increase the number of health providers. The challenge is the way the VMMC program was started with the provision of incentives. Also, identifying the type of cadre to be trained is a challenge.

Supply Chain: We need to have supplies managed by Medical Stores Limited (MSL). Let the procurement sit at MSL. There are some fears that some supplies may not reach the intended users. So, some implementing partners like CHAZ are not ready to move that direction.

Any high-level decisions on indicators?

In the past, most people were not able to access the platform for indicators. But now, program officers can easily access and track indicators. Indicators are no longer a problem. However, partners like CDC do not focus on infants but on Children above 10 years old.

So, who are the people, their roles and how are decisions made?

Technical Working Group (TWG) – Its difficult at xxxx but perhaps at director, Permanent Secretary and Minister xxxxx.

Which of these would you speak on?

For sustainability of VMMC programme, we need people to be accountable. I would like to see people employed for VMMC services. Let's have people be held accountable at each district. In that way, sustainability will be guaranteed.

As a province, we are providing leadership and we end up depending on the district staff. We need to follow-up targets at district and health facility level. **How?** By availability of resources (mobile couches etc). Emphasis should be placed on outreach. Accountability is happening but there is need for improvement.

How do you define the future state of Supply Chain?

Partners like CIDRZ, Society for Family Health (SFH) and CDC are concerned with centralized purchase and storing of supplies. CDC is advocating for centralized supply chain. Centralized buying maybe easier. However, we need to ensure that there are no stock-outs. We hope that there will be no red-tape processes. If it goes central, then we need assurance that requests will be processed quickly.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxx xxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxx

Date: 12th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxx xxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxxx. I have seen the VMMC programme grow. xxxxx partners, planning, resource mobilisation and monitoring of implementation. We have been supporting adolescents and infants. However, there has been efforts for young people. There was need to start discussing early infants and attempts were made to train some health care providers.

What is your understanding of sustainability of VMMC?

My view of sustainability is government to take over in terms of service delivery, training and partners should work with the government. We don't have a problem with adults but infants. We have not been providing enough support. Our staff are mobile, and they tend to leave with their skills. The funding we have from CDC COAG supports EIMC. Introducing interventions for early infants is the way to go as this will help to bridge the gap between the circumcised and uncircumcised.

What are decisions that that might be taking place in the future state where EIMC and EAMC are sustainable and integrated?

Policy: At provincial level, we don't develop policy but only implement. Province is only involved in discussions with MoH at national level. And MoH at national level then decides to make it policy or not. This is how we decided on EIMC. The discussions about infant circumcision started at the district level.

Do you think province need to coordinate with the national level? At national level, the province is part of the Technical Working Group.

Funding: We are encouraging integrated approach with other health services. Routine service delivery which is non-campaign dependent is happening in some facilities but at a slow pace.

Indicators: We have non-campaign targets. We are trying to make sure that every health facility has VMMC provider. But for the future, MoH might need to do more. Under EIMC and EAMC, supply chain is poor. For the future, this needs to be taken care of and is dependent on policy. Policy is overarching and it determines how we spend on training, supply chain etc. Policy comes from MoH national level. The province then customizes and decides on how to roll-out and disseminate the information down to health facility level.

Funding: Government gives specific funds to Lusaka Provincial Health Office to implement activities. Once this is done, then a gap analysis is conducted.

Indicators: These are determined at national level. The province then translates these indicators to weekly targets. For EIMC and EAMC, we would do the same. We can learn from the HIV programme which started with the district level. Even with the VMMC, we can start with national indicators and determine based on the statistics from the central statistical office.

What motivated the national to listen to the district? It was the district. For Lusaka district, CIDRZ generated the evidence and MoH had buy-in. Also, MoH has annual review meetings which are facilitated CHAI. In such meetings, recommendations are made. Out current Permanent Secretary for Technical Services has passion for VMMC work

and discussions on sustainability of VMMC have taken place. Sustainability is key and it is even be discussed at regional levels like SADC.

Any Challenges?

There is need to find someone to take the lead for VMMC and the position already exists. We have Deputy Director-HIV services, VMMC coordinator, Clinical Care specialist and Director Public Health and Director Clinical Care. xxxx is the VMMC xxxxxx and is better placed to comment on policy.

EIMC is already happening at health facility level. We need to start laying a foundation for scale-up

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No: + xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 26th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxx, lxxxxx at communicable diseases of which HIV is one of them. Among many interventions, we are focusing on prevention of HIV/AIDS and VMMC is one such key intervention. xxxx have robust activities and strategies and that that they are implemented appropriately and timely implemented. In additionxxxxx offer technical support on VMMC.

What does sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

Implementation of VMMC has mainly been donor-supported. Implementation Partners have helped to scale-up VMMC. CHAI has been a key partner on VMMC in Muchinga province and they have supported us with demand creation and supplies for VMMC.

Sustainability means that we need to start thinking of how to provide VMMC services when donor-support is not there.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

- a) **Policy:** Currently, VMMC been driven by campaigns. Implementation partners have not focused on EIMC. Therefore, we need to put up a policy to guide on EIMC to be part of service delivery. We need to shift policy to EIMC, and this can be incorporated in post-natal care. This will be less expensive.

Who might be involved in pushing the agenda to shift policy to EIMC?

Ministry of Health (MoH) is the prime to lead this agenda. And this can be done with the help of stakeholders at various levels through the Technical Working Groups at district and provincial level.

What might be the roles of each of the stakeholders?

What might be the decision-making for policy shift to EIMC? What are some of the decisions that may need to be made at your level?

- a) **Assess the capacity of MoH to offer EIMC service.** This will entail looking at the required human resources in relation to the health facilities. Currently, some provinces only have 1 provider. But in the sustainable future, it will be good to have providers in all the zonal health facilities.
- b) Engagement of lower level health staff at district and provincial levels.
- c) Call for a national indaba where all the findings of the assessment process will be shared with the stakeholders.
- d) **Appropriate policy direction made through the help of Permanent Secretary.**

What might be some barriers around shifting policy to EIMC? In terms of policy formulation, there will be minimal barriers. However, the main barrier would be on lack of capacity to implement EIMC. Are we ready to implement this approach in terms of capacity? We would need to engage the community members so that demand for EIMC is created. If we don't do enough, then service provision will be affected.

What might be some motivations for policy shift to EIMC? Sustainability of VMMC should be the major motivator. We would need to engage stakeholders and provide evidence why the current system of VMMC implementation is not sustainable. This should then make us focus on sustainability.

What might be the conditions necessary for the decisions to be made?

- a) We will need capacity in the form of human resources and trainings.
- b) We need to invest in information sharing. If you conduct a study on what health providers know about the National Operation Plan (NOP), you will discover that most of them do not know. In Muchinga Province, we reviewed the 8 pillars of NOP with the district health team. People were surprised with the information contained therein. We stated seeing the VMMC numbers going up. Therefore, information sharing as guided by NOP is critical. Infact, pillar 8 of NOP talks about sustainability and EIMC.
- c) **Funding:** Funding largely comes from implementation partners. Global Fund supports VMMC campaigns, CHAI provides technical support, meetings and monitoring. However, looking at the future, how can we establish financing based on 'National Health Insurance Scheme'? How can VMMC tap in the health care financing mechanisms? The National Health Insurance Scheme can be one sure way of financing VMMC activities. We may also provide VMMC services to those who may want to have VIP services for their children.

Who might be involved in making decisions on funding mechanism? The funds would mainly come through MoH at National Level. In terms of resource allocation, I would put more funds in supplies, trainings and fuel instead of allowances. The focus should be more of service provision.

What might be some barriers in making decisions around funding? We would expect minimal resistance due to withdrawal of allowances in the sustainable future. We may need to engage the stakeholders and health providers and present the facts that currently most men have been circumcised and need for EIMC.

Barriers may need to do with the perceived funding resistance and this calls for planning for VMMC programs. In the current situation, grants for health activities have not been coming. Even if they came, there will be those hard decisions of what activities need to be funded at district and provincial level.

a) Service delivery

The cost of providing VMMC services was high due to distances. It meant that teams had to go to communities. In order to bring services closer, it will be good to provide all the services in health facilities. We will need to train more providers and have more supplies

and equipment. We would need to integrate or routinise and decentralize VMMC services.

Who might be involved in making decisions on service delivery?

The Provincial Health Office (PHO) has mandate to provide support to District Health Office (DHO). Therefore, the province is in between policy formulation and implementation. PHO has the responsibility to solicit for support so that zonal health facilities can provide VMMC services. And this would be preceded with training of health providers.

What might be the steps in making decisions on integrate service delivery?

- a) Decision to integrate VMMC in other health service delivery will be made at provincial level.
- b) Provincial Health Office will mobilise local resources
- c) Provincial Health Office will then engage various stakeholders

What might be some barriers in making decisions around integration or decentralization of service delivery?

- a) Capacity will remain an issue
- b) Perception that health providers are denied opportunities to travel.
- c) Wrong perception about VMMC not being a priority by some health providers.

Trainings

As MoH, we have realized that in-service trainings are expensive to run. The issue of pre-service training for EIMC is important. The training should enhance knowledge to address key problems. Clinical Officers and other health providers will need to be drilled in EIMC. Training should enhance knowledge to address key problems. Pre-service training is more sustainable as it reduces training costs and generates more numbers for the VMMC program.

Who might be involved in making decisions on pre-service training? The curriculum development for pre-service training can be presented to the Technical Working Groups (TWGs) at district, provincial and national levels and it will need to be agreed upon. The training institutions are also part of the TWGs.

What might be the steps in making decisions on pre-service training?

- a) Provincial Health Director would present the proposal for EIMC to be part of pre-service training during the TWG meeting
- b) Document the action items arising from the TWG meeting

- c) Develop an action plans and justification for EIMC to be part of pre-service training.

When implemented, a lot of financial resources will be preserved.

What might be some barriers in making decisions around pre-service training?

Which cadre of health care providers should be focused on?

Is it clinical officers or nurses? Ideally, we would want both nurses and clinical officers to be trained. And training of nurses would require collaboration with General Nursing Council (GNC). Currently, we have seen that there is no difference in performance between clinical officers and nurses. In some cases, nurses have even performed better as far as service delivery of VMMC is concerned.

Supply Chain

Supply Chain is crucial. But the current scenario of centrally coordinating commodities has challenges related to unavailability of commodities when they are required. Provincial VMMC Coordinators tend to call the Medical Stores Limited (MSL) Coordinators and then arrangements are made to collect commodities from them.

We would want to decentralize the supply chain. xxxxx has MSL hub and health facilities can collect their commodities after requesting. However, the system needs to be strengthened such that reporting, and deliveries are integrated in the overall coordination of supply chain.

Who might be involved in making decisions on supply chain?

Supply Chain is managed by Department of Clinical Care under the MoH. The TWG at Provincial and District Level are also involved. Pharmacy Department will need to be more involved. PHO and DHO have the responsibility of presenting proposals for standardized approach on supply chain to PHO and PHO would then present the matter to MoH National level.

Indicators

Most of the indicators on VMMC focus on number of circumcised, number of those tested and number of negative circumcised among those aged 10 – 49 years. These current

indicators are okay. But as we move towards sustainable EIMC, we will need to capture exposed infants aged 0 – 12 months.

What might be the steps in making decisions on indicators?

This will be better done through the TWG. We have not invested much in monitoring and evaluation. There has been more emphasis on parallel reporting on indicators. The data in the system and in the reports are different. There were instances where Health Management Information System (HMIS) was reporting less due to the tools used in data collection. We need to manage the system and data entry clerks should be fully oriented. Unfortunately, the process of data entry was tied to allowances.

Cross-Ministry Collaboration

What is the current state of cross-ministry collaboration?

We have been xxxxxx with Ministry of Education (MOE). We use the MoE structures and pupils for VMMC activities. We have also xxxxx with Zambia National Information Services (ZANIS) for demand creation and also, Ministry of xxxxx Development. The other collaborators include Road Development Agency, Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs and partners like CHAI, EQUIP, JSI, Global Fund etc.

What new partnerships might you need to forge in the future state where EIMC and EAMC is sustainable and integrated?

MoH is focusing on primary health care. Therefore, the use of community structures such as Neighbourhood Health Committees (NHCs) will help us to mobilise or engage mothers to access services at the health facilities. We will also need to continue collaborating with traditional authorities such as headmen and chiefs. At provincial level, we will need to maintain collaboration with traditional partners like MoE, Ministry of Youths and Sports Development and Ministry of Community Development. We have also collaborated with the Provincial Traditional and Chiefs Officer and Chief Nkola

How has been your collaboration with Ministry of Education (MoE)?

xxxx has mainly engaged MoE at xxxxx. MoE at district level have a VMMC Coordinator who is even seconded to attend the District TWG Meetings. However, at xxxxx, we have not involved the office of the Provincial Education Officer. Moving forward, the Provincial TWG may need to deliberately have representation from the office of Provincial Education Officer during the TWGs that are held every quarter.

What might motivate you (in your role) to move towards sustainability?

a) It is this idea of efficient use of resources in which we need to do more with less.

b) It is a desire to meet our targets for VMMC without have a backlog. Because of this, we have declared that each month, is a campaign month for Muchinga province.

What are your greatest barriers?

We need to change the way of thinking for health providers. They need to stop focusing on allowances but look at HIV epidemic control. With this in mind, health providers are likely to be innovative.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name 1: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No. xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Name 2: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No. xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Name 3: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No. xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 25th xxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxx xxxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxx is involved in VMMC when they are invited to attend meetings. However, the invitations have not been regular. The last invitation to attend VMMC campaign was in April xxxx.

How has your collaboration been with Provincial Health Office?

We have collaborated more with the PHO on counseling and testing for HIV. When we invite our colleagues from PHO to assist with checking the health status of leaners, they tend to ask for allowances.

How might collaboration between Provincial Health Office and Provincial Education Office be strengthened?

This can be done in 3 main ways:

- a) Team planning and reviews between PEO and PHO and other line ministries. If we had a common meeting, we can list the activities that are happening in the province be it VMMC, HIV/AIDS, reproductive health etc.
- b) Implementation – Its one thing to plan and its another to implement. PHO staff tend to go in schools to talk to learners without the company of PEO staff.
- c) Policy – When the Ministry of Health changes policy on a matter that affects learners and teachers, they need to communicate to Ministry of Education. A good example is the new policy by MoH where abortion is allowed and yet as MoE, we have been telling learners not to use contraceptives.

Who might be better placed to move the agenda for enhanced collaboration between PHO and PEO? The PHO should move the agenda and call us to a meeting.

The Ministry of Education believes in Child protection and is better placed to collaborate with Ministry of Health even on VMMC. MoE has many learners in schools and with proper information sharing, MoE can be a good agent of change by influencing the mindsets of both learners and teachers.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organization: xxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 25th xxxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxxx

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

- a) **Service Delivery:** VMMC has problems because we are picking staff with other tasks. We have trained so many staff who are committed to other duties in most health centers. Therefore, they are returned to their sections after VMMC trainings hence

causing shortage and disruption of service. VMMC always suffers because it has limited specifically assigned staffs.

VMMC will need to be a unit to provide normal routine service. It needs to be coordinated by a focal point person at all levels who can only focus on VMMC.

Who might be involved in making decisions on service delivery?

- a) District health Director
- b) District clinical care specialist
- c) Maternal and Child Health coordinator
- d) Public Health Officer
- e) Community engagement officer
- f) Health Officer

What might be the process in decision-making for service delivery?

- a) Management meetings to discuss creation of VMMC units.
- b) Hold a meeting with Medical Superintendent, Hospital administration, Senior Nursing Officer, Head of Theatre Department, Surgeons etc. Hospital in creation of VMMC unit. This would work best if the hospital is involved because they have manpower.
- c) Invite the Provincial VMMC coordinator to attend the meeting to discuss the creation of VMMC unit at district level.
- d) Establishment of VMMC Unit.

What might be some barriers around decision on service delivery:

Manpower is a challenge because of limited trained staff to support VMMC. Infrastructure and transport are other challenges that might affect decisions on service delivery.

How might these challenges be overcome? Transportation challenges can be addressed by having a vehicle designated for VMMC activities just like departments like Blood bank and eye have their own transport. It would also be good to integrate VMMC services.

What might be some motivations around decisions on service delivery?

VMMC Programme at National level has given us some targets and Muchinga province is lagging. The motivation is that VMMC will be self-identified and independent and have own resources like the way the eye departments operates.

Supply Chain: we need to move away from dependence on partners to provide supplies. Supplies for VMMC can be integrated with other general supplies. Therefore, there is need to plan for the logistics.

Who might be involved in making decisions on supply chain? District health Directors, Clinical care specialists, Planners and Pharmacists will need to be involved in ensuring that commodities are available and distributed respectively.

What might be the decision-making process on supply chain?

- a) Hold a Therapeutic Committee Meeting together with Pharmacy, Laboratory and X-ray departments. When VMMC is a unit, then we can be heard in such meetings.
- b) Need to plan for logistical package in collaboration with health facilities, District Health Directors, Pharmacists and District Planner.
- c) District Health Director will request health facilities to submit budgets for VMMC logistics and commodities.
- d) The Planner will consolidate the district and provincial budgets
- e) Provincial Health Director will submit plans and budgets to Ministry of Health who will in turn submit to Ministry of Finance.

In terms of the flow of information,) Leadership team at Neighbourhood Health Committee (NHC) level communicate to the Overall In-Charge at health facility level. The Overall In-Charge at health facility level communicates to the District Health Director and Management Team. The District Health Director and Management Team communicates to the Provincial Health Director and Management Team and from the province information flows to Ministry of Health National level.

District Health Director and the Medical Superintendent would communicate to staff that from now on-wards we will approach the VMMC program in this manner and as such a process would take some time. I would then go down to the health facility level and discuss with them regarding the same. This would help to bring about empowerment, responsibility and improved and consistent supply.

What might be some barriers in making decisions on supply chain? Potential barriers might be stock-outs at MSL and fear of additional duties to already over stretched staff.

How might you overcome the barriers in making decisions on supply chain? The district could use the 4% budget allocation to buy some commodities from local pharmaceutical traders.

What might be the motivators for making decisions on supply chain?

Mpika has a hub for supply chain managed by Medical Stores Limited. With sustainability, we will be able to make decisions on VMMC and be guaranteed of supplies.

What might motivate you (in your role) to move towards sustainability?

- a) This region is non-circumcising. It will help us to eliminate HIV by 2030
- b) Help reduce cervical cancer in our women
- c) Help reduce STIs

What are your greatest barriers? Many people trained as providers but few practicing. We need to change provider perceptions around the program because they are demotivated without allowances. We need to train staff who are self-motivated and ensure proper scrutiny before training

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organization: xxxxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 25th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxx, I oversee all health services in the province. Programmatically act as a xxxx to ensure programs including xxxxx run smoothly by sourcing and managing enablers i.e. resources from government and donors. Further, ensures inclusion of line ministries such as Traditional affairs, Education, Sports and Community Development respectively.

What does sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

All programs supported by donors scare me because of the day they will announce that they are cutting funding. Over dependency on donor is a dangerous way to operate and run programs. It is mandate of government and health system to provide health services.

Sustainability means domesticating VMMC activities into routine service delivery.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

Policy: We need to come up with strict decision to encourage people go for EIMC. It is a cheaper and easier way to conduct VMMC. Therefore, there is need for policy formulation in the future to guide this process. Muchinga Province has never had EIMC there, policy at high level would be very key.

Who might be involved in pushing the agenda to shift policy to EIMC?

We as key leaders need to push for this policy. We need to push the agenda through Permanent Secretary Ministry of Health (MoH), cabinet and ultimately parliament to make law.

What might be the steps for decision-making for policy shift?

Hold a stakeholders meeting and discuss sustainability and propose for adoption of EIMC policy. The stakeholders meeting would be key.

What might be some barriers around shifting policy to EIMC? Cultural challenges since Muchinga province is a non-circumcising province. The other barriers would political environment. Certain programmes which are introduced may be used to de-campaign the Government.

What might help to overcome the barriers? Cultural challenges are better addressed through community sensitizations. As for political environment, we need to continuously engage with those concerned and this can be resolved using multi sectoral approaches.

What might be some motivations for policy shift to EIMC? If we present the facts about VMMC and its role in prevention of HIV/AIDS, this should be the major motivator. This is the one thing that can be used for policy shift to EIMC. Effective engagement of stakeholders and provide reasons why there must be a system change.

Funding: Not much funding coming from central government. Further, there should not be any specific funding for VMMC. We need to integrate resource allocation into what we are already doing. Currently, funding is largely from donors and implementation partners.

Who might be involved in making decisions on funding? Provincial Implementors need to ensure that we start teaching our colleagues that there is a policy shift from vertical programming to integration even as far as service delivery is concerned. Provincial Health Director level would need to drive the process. The funds would mainly come through MoH at National Level.

We will need to educate our colleagues about this shift in funding using information, education and communication (IECs).

What might be the decision-making process on integration? The Provincial Health Director would start with the District Health Director and the Medical Superintendent. xxxxx that from now on-wards we will approach the VMMC program in this manner and as such a process would take some time. I would then xxxxx health facility level and negotiate with them about the same.

What might be some barriers in making decisions around integration? At implementation level, I foresee resistance from health care providers because when you talk about VMMC, it's about allowances or money to staff. The other barrier is space. We have so many other programmes running. To get buy-in would be helpful.

What might help overcome the barriers around integration? On resistance from health care providers, we need to put up a strong policy.

And how might this process of putting up a strong policy be? It has to start with the Permanent Secretary of Ministry of Health, and it will cascade down to the Provincial Health Director level. It is the Permanent Secretary who issues out instructions. In addition, calling for a stakeholders meeting with Permanent Secretary and partners would be key.

In terms of space, this can easily be resolved overnight at the level of Provincial Health Director.

What might be the motivators facilitating decisions around integration? The motivation lies in the fact that we will not always have donors for the VMMC programme. When the donor says that support is withdrawn, then it can be difficult.

Trainings

There should not be a separate training for VMMC providers. The current curriculum for health care providers needs to be enhanced to support VMMC so that we move away from stand-alone trainings. If the focus is sustainability, then in-service trainings are too costly.

Who might be involved in making decisions on pre-service training? Provincial Health Directors and his team of provincial implementers.

We first have to identify the gaps and then we communicate to Permanent Secretary of Health. The Permanent Secretary will involve other stakeholders such as General Nursing Council (GNC) and the Health Professions Council of Zambia (HPCZ) in order to agree to put VMMC training curriculum in pre-service training. Technical Working Groups (TWGs) at national level will need to be involved too.

What might be the steps in making decisions on pre-service training?

- a) Provincial Health Director present the proposal for EIMC to be part of pre-service training to PS.
- b) PS moves the motion to national TWG meeting for discussion and consideration.

What might be some barriers in making decisions around pre-service training?

The trainers for pre-service may not be specialists in curriculum.

What might help to overcome the barrier on pre-service training? It may be good to focus on Trainer of Trainers for pre-service training.

What might be some motivation in making decisions around pre-service training?

The high cost of a separate VMMC training should act as motivation. Once the training is integrated in the pre-service curriculum, a lot of resources will be saved for other needy areas.

Indicators

Is there a gap between the current indicators being measured in VMMC and what you might measure in the future sustainable state?

Number of male infants born compared to those circumcised. Ideally, the number of infants born and those circumcised should be equal.

Is EIMC happening in Muchinga Province? We do not have the EIMC Policy yet. Ideally, medical doctors should be a position to perform EIMC procedures but equipment like morgan clamp is not available.

Cross-Ministry Collaboration

What is the current state of cross-ministry collaboration?

We are enjoying very good collaboration with line Ministries such as Ministry of Education (MOE). We use the MoE structures and pupils for VMMC activities. We have also collaborated with Ministry of Youths, Sports and Child Development, Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs and Ministry of Community Development. We can also collaborate with the media.

How might you order or priorities the decisions based on the categories?

We are usually encouraged to spend more time on planning. In terms of priority, the list would be:

- a) Policy should be first. If you don't have direction you can't go anywhere.
- b) Need for start-up funding to implement the activities.
- c) Then, training, supply chain and indicators can then follow.

What might motivate you (in your role) to move towards sustainability?

1. Adoption of the program will help reduce at the cost
2. It will be conducted within the framework of what I can afford because the current state is not the right way to go. Where would I get money to pay health providers? Cost is what will motivate me.

What are your greatest barriers?

“Hang over effect” this is where people are used to current state so new state would be difficult to adopt to. Hence, transition should be gradual. It should start with mindset change of health workers country wide and also disseminate the information to others

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organization: xxxxxxxxxx

No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 19th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regards to VMMC?

My role is xxxx the implementation in its entire cascade.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

This means continuing to run the program without supporting partners. It also means the VMMC program without partner support.

How might the VMMC programme run without allowances for health care providers?

We have done it for the ART programme, so it is possible even for VMMC programme.

Which of these seven categories might you be comfortable to discuss with us? We can focus on service delivery.

What might be some conditions necessary for decision-making on service delivery in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

- a) Capacity building: We had slightly over 100 male circumcision (MC) providers trained. But almost half have been lost due to attrition and pursuit of jobs elsewhere. We need to ensure therefore that each and every health facility has an MC provider.
- b) Financing aspect: Government should be taking a leading role in the provision of VMMC commodities. Currently, VMMC activities depends on donors. Government may need to fund service delivery.
- c) Infrastructure: Most of these health facilities were built a long time ago. So the delivery of services in health facilities has expanded but the space has remained the same. Space is therefore a challenge.
- d) Transport: We may need to do a lot of investments in transport like bicycles and motorbikes so that health facilities are able to provide good service that is closer to the people. Most of the health facilities service patients who cover a distance of about 30 kilometers.
- e) Routinization of service delivery: In xxxx, for instance, we trained about 6 MC providers but only 2 are active in service provision.

What might be the process in decision-making for funding for service delivery?

Ministry of Health through the health insurance policy is an alternative source of funding. The National Health Insurance Scheme is a good funding option. Resources can be distributed to support the VMMC programme. In addition, active community participation and we can reach out to well-wishers and community-driven projects for help.

What might be the decision-making process for routinizing service delivery?

- a) We need to put in place a well-defined structure that supports service delivery for VMMC. At Ministry of Health headquarters, we have a structure We also need to put in place a defined structure at provincial and district level that with specified and well-defined job descriptions.
- b) We need to come up with a policy on dedicated MC providers.
- c) We need dedicated space and supportive and mobilizing teams in place. The critical thing is to ensure that the program is not separate but integrated into the entire health system.

Who might be involved in process of making decisions on service delivery?

- a) VMMC structures: Ministry of Health Headquarters needs to take the lead. Based on the VMMC pillars, it should start from policy makers and all stakeholders at provincial, district and facility level need to be involved. Right now, the VMMC programme has a tag of being supported by implementation partners.
- b) MC providers: This can be done at facility or hospital level and community level especially for identifying community champions.
- c) Mobilizing Team: This can be done at health facility level to enhance ownership.

What might be your thoughts on integrating VMMC into service delivery? When we started the ART programme, it was not integrated. We need to have an integrated service delivery system. This is working well in some health facilities like in Limulunga where there is a men's clinic operating in an integrated system.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on service delivery?

- a) Inadequate human resources
- b) Inadequate Infrastructure
- c) Inadequate Funding of programmes
- d) Inadequate consumables and surgical equipment

What might help to overcome the barriers?

- a) Inadequate human resources: At xxxx General Hospital, there is only 1 person doing EIMC. We could be thinking of on-site orientation. Adding these into pre- service training curriculum for nurses and clinical officers may help. As babies are born, they male need to go for circumcision. We also need to review the current curriculum for midwives.
- b) Inadequate infrastructure: PEPFAR funds cannot be used for construction. This is where the Government may need to come in.

What might be the decision-making process on rolling out pre-service training?

Different decision makers at different levels should be able to make decisions on that.

Regulatory bodies such as General Nursing Council and Health Professions Council of Zambia need to be engaged by government through Ministry of Health to incorporate VMMC package and approve the pre-service training.

- a) Policy makers and stakeholders may need to meet to discuss.
- b) When this is done, then rolling out pre-service training, implementation, training of cadres which should be done at pre-service training level as opposed to in-service which is very expensive and unsustainable.
- c) Putting the guidelines in job descriptions for MC providers.
- d) Also, VMMC should be included in staff appraisals with clear key result areas.

What might be the motivators for making decisions?

If I am to do my work effectively, I would need necessary skills, knowledge, space and consumables.

What might be your priority list based on the seven categories?

- a) Policy
- b) Training
- c) Cross- Ministry Collaboration
- d) Supply Chain
- e) Service Delivery
- f) Indicators

What new indicators might you measure in the sustainable future?

When you look at the tool for conducting performance assessment (PA2) at health facility level, there is no indicator on VMMC. If we have to be sustainable, there is need for policy makers at Ministry of Health headquarters to revise the PA2 Tool. We also need to have indicators that track early infants i.e. from 0 to 12 months or 0 to 60 days

What new partnerships might you need to forge in the future state where EIMC and EAMC is sustainable and integrated?

Ministry of health will need to partner with key players such as the midwifery association of Zambia, Surgical society of Zambia and traditional circumcision in order to achieve a sustainable VMMC program. We can also engage with Traditional Healers Association of Zambia (TAPAZ).

Do you think midwives might be better placed to be MC providers in view of their short supply in most health facilities?

We need to leverage on midwives. Midwives are being trained in MC in Western Province. This may help with targets for VMMC programme.

What are your greatest barriers?

1. The greatest barrier is human resource that is inadequate MC providers to meet the demand.
 2. Infrastructure and equipment are also other major challenges.
 3. Funding from Government. MTEF plans have nothing on VMMC and as such the VMMC programme has dependent on implementation partners
 4. At district level, there are challenges with ownership of VMMC programme.
-

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organization: xxxxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 19th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regards to VMMC?

xxxx xxxxx to ensure good recovery. Further, xxxx xxxxx into issues to do with xxxx supply.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

This would mean the ability of Provincial Health Office to continue to offer services with or without donor support. We do not need donors to conduct circumcision in our society. It has always been there hence, there is no need for us to pay people allowances to provide the service. The traditional system of circumcision is already self-sustaining in most cultures that are still practicing therefore, it can stand on its own.

Which of these seven categories do you feel comfortable to discuss with us? We can focus on service delivery.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

- a) **Service Delivery:** the people offering this service should know that this has been there in the before. Therefore, we need to tap into the already existing knowledge and bridge the gaps with new technology. This would entail:
- b) Engagement with the traditional authorities and Ministry of Health at different levels.
- c) Understand and appreciate each other's positions.
- d) Then come up with common ground between traditional and new technology if we are to make this program sustainable in the future. It will help to service delivery which is sustainable at both ends.

Who might be involved in making decisions on service delivery?

- a) Ministry of Health
- b) Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional affairs
- c) Ministry of Education
- d) Ministry of Guidance and Religious Affairs
- e) Ministry of Community Development and Social Welfare

How is the collaboration with line Ministries?

The cross-Ministry collaboration is not very strong. Ministry of Health is driving programs on their own because it's their agenda. Ministry of Health can drive the agenda based on the scientific understanding of VMMC since they have the personnel, infrastructure and the commodities. However, the collaboration should be stronger, and more stakeholders as mentioned above involved in order to have a buy in at all stages. This should mainly be at planning and implementation stages. For example, Ministry of Education can be very instrumental in mobilizing students and learners while Ministry of Community Development has the structures that can be used to effectively achieve results.

What might be some barriers around decision on service delivery:

The major barriers would be Religious beliefs, cultural beliefs, myths and misconceptions, lack of funding, political setup and mismanagement of resources.

What might help to overcome the challenges on decisions on service delivery?

- a) Financial mis-management would be overcome through proper accountability systems.
- b) As for cultural, religious and myths, we need engagement and cross pollination of ideas with the community.

c) In terms of political set up, we need to ensure that support is de-linked from politicians.

What might be some motivations around decisions on service delivery?

The motivation is the proven benefits of VMMC. It protects men and women from infections such as HIV and cervical cancer respectively. In this sense, it is a good intervention and the benefits have been scientifically proven.

The motivation is that there is more benefit especially if it is done at EIMC stage than EAMC. The two therefore, need to be brought together. It should be the whole cascade if we have to offer a comprehensive service.

What might be some conditions necessary for decision-making on service delivery?

We have the human resources, infrastructure and the population. All the fundamentals are there. Its just a matter of modalities. I wished we had integrated VMMC with the existing service delivery and programmes. All stakeholders should be involved as part of the integration process. The idea should be that Ministry of Health provides leadership and sets the agenda.

What might be your priority list of these seven categories?

- a) Policy is key This is because it defines everything and is fundamental. With policy, you are able to align all the other seven categories
- b) Then, you can allocate funding resources according to what is needed.
- c) Cross Ministry Collaboration

Indicators?

We should focus on EIMC and EAMC as they help with reducing HIV infections. Then, we also need to report on indicators related to EIMC and EAMC.

What are your greatest barriers?

- a) Non- integration of VMMC programs with other services offered by Ministry of Health, is a barrier.
- b) The project mode nature of VMMC. Over dependence on donor support. Furthermore, why not introduce VMMC training to be part of the curriculum for training of all cadre of students in health. This then would ensure sustainability of service delivery.

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organization: xxxxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 18th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regards to VMMC?

xxxxxx. As xxxxxx all health services in the xxxxxx. It means tracking of service delivery, quality in accordance with standard operating procedures. Furthermore, monitoring and ensuring targets are xxxxx to contribute to the provincial targets. xxxxx capacity building, mentorships and training of health providers.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

There are currently 32 static sites and 285 mobile sites for MC. This means service delivery is more outreach based and this is not sustainable. Therefore, we need to ensure that the VMMC program is anchored more in the general service provision at facility level. E.g. Maternal child health. This will make EIMC more sustainable. It also means having dedicated funding and personnel, strengthened static service provision and make it available in front line. Integration of VMMC in health service delivery is the way to go. We also need capacity building of health providers. Training of health providers on VMMC should shift from in-service to pre-service

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

- a) Policy:** It will be difficult to integrate EAMC but would rather focus on the EIMC. There should be policy therefore, to drive that agenda. EAMC should be anchored within HIV/AIDS or existing services because I feel it will be difficult to come up with policy that will bring adolescents to seek services separately. We need policy guidelines therefore around EIMC and build a cadre of providers that will focus and deliver the service in local facilities.

Which cadre of providers might you have in mind? The key people are nurses and clinical officers. Medical Officers and Licentiates will need to be strengthened. We need to monitor the set of skills.

We need to move towards Pre- service training. Clearly this is the most sustainable and cost-effective way to go. We can look at incorporating VMMC component in the existing curriculum for doctors, medical licentiates, clinical officers, theatre nursing and general nursing. For Level 1 health facilities, we may need to think about theatres where VMMC can be delivered. VMMC for neo-natal infants can then be handled by the theatre nurses.

Who might be involved in pushing the agenda to shift policy to EIMC?

Policy is a function of MoH Head Quarters. They should take the lead but need representation from key stakeholders at different levels. This may include Provincial, and sub-national levels such as district and facility. For Western Province, xxxxx some cultural issues at play and therefore engagement with the community especially those that conduct traditional circumcision is key. This is because it becomes easy to work when you have a buy-in from traditional authorities. More importantly, you need political will to change the policy.

Who might be involved in making decisions around policy shift?

- a) Ministry of Health Headquarters in Lusaka has the overarching responsibility. Office. Training unit of Ministry of Health would be key in this regard.
- b) Also, engagement with various training institutions is important.
- c) General Nursing Council (GNC) in this regard is a key partner.
- d) Health Professionals council of Zambia (HPCZ)

What might be some barriers around decision on policy shift?

Barriers may not necessarily be policy level but not having enough resources to drive this agenda. Therefore, political will would be key. But potential barriers would be in the form of implementation challenges such as availability of funds.

Dedicated Funding: Policy would need to be broken down into strategic plan and costed to understand the resources required to implement. We will need to have a plan that is costed.

How might the strategic plan be funded? Government will need to take the lead. There is need to think about how we can leverage from cooperating partners, private sector and private-public partnerships. There is also the National Health Insurance Scheme which has a 'benefits package'. If we have to talk of sustainability, we may need to include EIMC and EAMC to be part of the 'benefits package'.

What might be some barriers around decisions on dedicated funding?

VMMC programme operating in isolation is a potential barrier. We need consistent funding for sustainability to be guaranteed. Our focus should be on local ownership of the VMMC programme.

What might be the motivators in making decisions on dedicated funding?

VMMC is a key programme for response towards HIV.

Supply Chain: This would stem from funding. With the policy shift and re-branding of Medical Stores Limited (MSL), MoH will need to set up a drug fund so that money is available at all time.

What might be the decision-making process on supply chain?

Ministry of health would need to engage with Medical Stores Limited to ensure procurement of VMMC commodities and moving it to provincial hubs and eventually to implementing sites. Ministry of Health Headquarters would be key together with MSL and key partners in terms of commodity availability and distribution. The key steps in decision-making on supply chain will entail the following:

- a) There will be need for discussions supply chain and this should involve the logistics unit of Ministry of Health, MSL, partners and funders like PEPFAR and Global Fund.
- b) VMMC commodities will need to be categorized under essential commodities list. And this will require some capacity building.
- c) Health facilities should be able to order directly from MSL and follow the supply chain. It should entail VMMC commodities move from central MSL to provincial hubs and then to implementation health facilities.
- d) **Indicators:** District Health Management Information System (DHIS) is lagging but is improving in terms of programmatic data capturing. Normally there are anomalies with data.

What might be the decision-making process on indicators?

- a) The M&E unit and Public Health unit at Ministry of Health Headquarters would need to meet and agree on the key indicators for VMMC in the future state which sustainable.
- b) We will need to have disaggregated data with different age brackets for neo-natal. It could be 1 – 5 yrs, 5 – 14 years and adults.
- c) It is also important to include quality indicators that capture commodity availability and monitoring of adverse events (AEs).

The program needs Indicators that speak to quality of service and commodity availability. The DHIS must track all program indicators. This also entails having registers need to be up to date and all other data collecting tools at the service

delivery point. This may require front line staff to be oriented on tools, data collection process and how to report.

Cross- Ministry Collaboration:

What is the current state of cross-ministry collaboration?

The cross-Ministry collaboration is not as it should be. Much more needs to be done to ensure we strengthen this if we are to move towards sustainability. The key ministries that we currently collaborate with are Ministry of Education, Ministry of Chiefs Affairs and Ministry of youth and sports.

How do you see the VMMC program without allowances?

We need to make the service more static to reduce on cost of travelling for outreach which essentially demands payment of allowances. Further, we need to effectively engage all providers into understanding that the service is now routine and not separate because there is no more funding.

What are your greatest barriers? My greatest barriers would be resources. Huge investments will be required for us to reach a sustainable state. We will need infrastructure, capacity-building, commodities etc. Therefore the front load approach would be the right way to go. We would need a good policy and strategy to move forward.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 19th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxx of VMMC programme at xxxxxlevel.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

It means continuity of service delivery by having a paediatric male circumcision (MC) provider. Currently, we do not have a paediatric male circumcision provider in Sioma District and this is an opportunity to expand the VMMC programme. The district trained some MC providers, but some are not practicing and as such, the only static sites are Sioma and Sitoti.

At district level, the Clinical Care Officer is overwhelmed with coordinating the T.B programme and other tasks. There is need for a VMMC coordinator who can focus on supply chain and training. The Clinical Care Officer is a trained MC provider and there are two others who are not active.

Looking at the seven categories on the decision mapping framework, which one might you feel comfortable to have a discussion with us?

Service Delivery

What decisions on service delivery might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infact Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

Need for Paediatric MC providers: We will need a hospital set-up and also to create demand since we are likely to get VMMC numbers from the children population.

Who might be involved in making decisions on Paediatric MC providers?

When Ministry of Health decides that all hospitals should have Paediatric MC providers, then it will be expected that the Provincial Health Office will have to drive this agenda in Western Province.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on Paediatric MC providers?

The main barriers will have to do with resources in the form of human and equipment.

- a) Human Resources: xxxx 1 clinical officer, a medical licentiate and a medical officer.
- b) Equipment: xxxxxno equipment to facilitate paediatric MC.

What might help to overcome the barriers on Paediatric MC providers?

Ministry of Health at National Level will need to prioritise allocation of resources to support Paediatric MC providers.

What might be the motivators in making decisions on Paediatric MC providers?

- a) The numbers for adult male circumcision are almost saturated.
- b) Since there is no Paediatric MC provider in Sioma district, it will be good to have one who can also be able to work in other districts of Western Province that do not have Paediatric MC providers.
- c) Ministry of Health needs to create a position for VMMC coordinator at district level who can support health facilities. With sustainability, the Paediatric MC provider will be more dedicated to work on VMMC activities.
- d) **Training of MC providers:** The expectation will be once MC providers are trained, they will need to contribute to better service delivery by increasing numbers of male circumcised.

What might be the key decisions that need to take place on training of MC providers?

- a) VMMC Coordinator would need to identify those to be trained at district level.
- b) VMMC Coordinator will need to be trained so that he/she takes charge of supply chain, management of consumables for VMMC and others.
- c) VMMC Coordinator will need to set targets so that progress is clearly monitored.

Who might be involved in the decision-making process on training of MC providers?

- a) VMMC Coordinator, Pharmacists etc.
- b) Technicians to take care of VMMC equipment
- c) Clinical Care Officer to respond to any cases of adverse events that may require further management.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on training of MC providers?

- a) Low education or literacy levels are likely to affect training in the district.
- b) Cultural beliefs such as Mukanda ceremony and perceptions that VMMC should not be conducted in hot season.
- c) Lack of interest on the VMMC and its related benefits.
- d) Most health facility In-Charges do not own VMMC programme.

What might help to overcome the barriers in making decisions on training of MC providers?

- a) On lack of ownership, we need to give In-Charges of health facilities proper communication and emphasise the benefits of VMMC to the clients. One main benefit being the fight against HIV infections.
- b) On low literacy levels, there is need to encourage community members to go to school so that they can understand messages on VMMC.
- c) On cultural beliefs, we need to involve indunas and chiefs in the VMMC programme and highlight the benefits of VMMC.

What might be the motivators for making decisions on training of MC providers?

- a) VMMC's contribution towards reducing HIV infections among the circumcised men.
- b) VMMC helps men to be hygienic.
- c) VMMC contributes to prevention of cervical cancer.
- d) VMMC can be an avenue for sex education especially among the adolescents.

What might be the necessary conditions necessary for decisions to be made on service delivery in the sustainable future where EIMC and EAMC is integrated?

- a) Need for resources i.e. human, equipment, commodities and supplies.
- b) Need for social mobilization and this will require collaboration with traditional authorities and administrative officers.
- c) **Cross Ministry Collaboration**

What new partnerships might we need to forge in the future state where EIMC and EAMC is sustainable and integrated?

We are part of the district council meetings. And xxxx collaborate with chiefs through the indunas. On the other hand, our collaboration with Ministry of Education needs improvement. The office of the District Education Board Secretary (DEBS) restricted the district health office from talking to learners about VMMC due to messages on sex education which were communicated to learners. Ideally, these cross-ministry collaborations may need to continue in the sustainable future.

In terms of forging new partnerships, we may need to collaborate with UNICEF who have a school feeding programme for children under the age of 5 years. The Ministry of Community Development and Social services can help us with social mobilisation.

What are your greatest barriers?

- a) Lack of support from MoH national level. Without support from national level, the VMMC programme cannot succeed.

- b) Lack of equipment to provide VMMC services to clients.
 - c) Human Resources. If there is no one who is able to provide the VMMC service, we can make use of the trainer of trainers, but funding is an issue. In this vein, training of pre-service students in VMMC will be good . We can therefore include clinical officers, medical licentiates etc.
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Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 18th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

How might you describe your collaboration with the Provincial Health Office (PHO)?

We have had joint meetings with PHO and traditional leaders on xxxxx sensitisation. These meetings were aimed at soliciting support from traditional leaders. We have also had meetings on sanitation, maternal health and HIV/AIDS. We have been trying to lobby for support from chiefs and suggest new ways of doing things. Traditional leaders are instrumental and therefore engaging them is key. Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs engages chiefs on varied issues. PHO's office collaborates with Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs whenever they need to engage the district chiefs in Western Province.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

It is about how the VMMC programme can be sustained.

How do you see the VMMC programme in light of the culture in Western Province? What advice can you give us for to have sustainable VMMC Programmes?

- a) Engagement of traditional leaders is key. This engagement is done at different levels i.e. district, chiefs and headman level. The hierarchy of the traditional administrative structures is as follows:

Subjects →Village Headman Kuta →Silalanda Kuta →Silalo Kuta →District Kuta →Siikako kuta

- b) Ensuring that the messages on VMMC are simple and understandable. The subjects in Western Province prefer to be talked to or engaged using silozi language. The messages on VMMC should also be disseminated in such a way that the focus is on the positives of VMMC and not the negatives.
- c) There is need for consistency in dissemination and delivery of messages. One-off programmes are not good.

How might we share messages on VMMC in non-circumcising communities of Western Province?

It is important that the messages on VMMC should emphasise the medical aspects of male circumcision as opposed to the traditional aspects.

What strategies might we use for sustainable EIMC and EAMC?

- a) Teenagers tend to be easily influenced. And they easily respect and listen to traditional authorities.
- b) In terms of social mobilisation or demand creation, it is important to penetrate the already existing community-based structures such as those for water and sanitation, community development etc.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 13th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

xxxxxx Department. We look at prevention of communicable diseases. VMMC is well placed in this xxxxxxxx HIV.

xxxxx of communicable diseases, xxxxxxxx under MoH. The xxxx xxxx xxxx coordination and reporting.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

It means continuing with a particular state in an already existing system. If we look at the VMMC programme, we are moving from external funders to Government funding.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

We might need to make decisions on the need to have male circumcision (MC) providers and also need for policy direction on circumcising babies i.e. EIMC within a short period of time after being born.

Who might be involved in the key decisions made?

Decisions on MC providers will mainly be made by Directorates of Public Health and Clinical Care Unit as well as the Human Resources under Ministry of Health.

1a) What might be decision-making process on having MC providers?

- a) A series of meetings involving Public Health, Clinical Care and Human Resources Units under Ministry of Health (MoH) will need to take place.
- b) The meetings should result in a clear guidance regarding EIMC and EAMC.
- c) Guidelines will need to be developed to guide health care providers in VMMC service delivery.
- d) Training of health care providers on the same developed guidelines.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on having MC providers?

- a) Workload given that the reproductive unit is already busy at MoH.
- b) Space – where would EIMC and EAMC happen at health facility level
- c) Supplies – where would the supplies come from?

What might help to overcome the barriers on having MC providers?

- a) Workload: It is sharing the benefits of male circumcision and how much costs will be saved by circumcising the male population. Therefore, the emphasis should be on the economic gains to MoH.

b) Space and Supplies: It will be good to conduct an assessment of equipment, supplies and infrastructure.

What might be the motivators in making decisions on having MC providers?

- a) With the high HIV infection rates among the adolescent population, the motivation is to reduced HIV infections in the population.
- b) With MC providers in health facilities, the staff under Clinical Care and Public Health will have times to focus on other activities or interventions and this will reduce their workload.

What might be some of the necessary conditions for making decisions on MC providers?

- a) MoH may need to estimate the current numbers of MC providers.
- b) MoH will need to look at the current MC providers in the health facilities. Since we are talking of sustainable EIMC and EAMC, do we need to train midwives?
- c) It is important to look at the current staffing levels so that other activities and interventions are not affected.
- d) Should there be a shortage of staff, there may be need to employ other cadre of staff.

Who might be better placed to be MC provider considering that midwives are generally in short supply?

Midwives are indeed in short supply. However, it depends with how busy the maternal wards are. For some health facilities that record a lot of births, clinical officers and nurses can play the role of MC providers while in health facilities that record 1 – 2 births in a day, the midwives can still be MC providers.

What might be your thoughts on sustainable EAMC?

We are trying to see how the health system can address the needs of adolescents. We may need to brainstorm on adolescents in terms of where they may need to be circumcised from. The younger adolescents are not fussy but the older adolescents. Some may prefer to be circumcised in the general surgical theatres while others may not. It would still be okay for them to be a surgical list for minor operations.

1b) Policy direction on circumcising babies i.e. EIMC

This requires an actual policy to be in place on what happens to babies when they are born. Currently, EIMC is not offered routinely in health facilities. And MoH at national level is better placed to make policy directives on this.

The process, barriers, how to overcome barriers, motivations and necessary conditions discussed under policy for MC providers, will still apply under EIMC policy direction.

a) Funding

We are looking at having a funding basket for health interventions and MC would benefit from this funding basket.

What might be the key decisions that need to take place on funding?

- 4) Expand the current budget line on VMMC. This will help the VMMC programme to have more resources.
- 5) Integration of VMMC services with other health service delivery.

Who might be involved in the decision-making process on funding?

It is Ministry of Health (Directorate of Public Health, Pharmacy) and Ministry of Finance and National Planning for resource allocations to different programmes.

What might be the decision-making process?

Decisions on funding in the health sector would need to be tabled before parliament. The key steps entail:

- a) Developing work plans and budget on VMMC
- b) Submit the work plans to Department of Planning of MoH National level
- c) Submission of plans to Ministry of Finance and National Development by Permanent Secretary of MoH
- d) Plans will be tabled before parliament by Minister of Finance and National Development
- e) Minister of Health will defend the plans and budgets at parliament
- f) MoH will need to conduct some advocacy work with parliamentarians and civil society organisations so that they can understand the proposal for expanding the current budget line on VMMC.

With the implementation of the National Insurance Scheme, MoH is looking at making use of the dug basket fund even for VMMC activities.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on funding?

- a) MoH has competing health needs and this may be overcome through advocacy.
- b) Competition of financial resources for other key national needs such as funds for elections, disasters etc.

How might the VMMC programme operate without partner involvement?

It is possible to integrate VMMC activities to be part of service delivery. We are almost achieving targets for the operational plan. If we look at the operational plan, we still have other males who are not yet circumcised. There is still work to be covered and moving towards EIMC will be beneficial for the VMMC programme.

How might the VMMC programme operate without allowances for MC providers?

We need to change the mindset of MC providers and we have tried to implement MC without allowances.

Is there a policy on allowances under MoH?

Policy on provision of allowances is already there. If I am providing a health service, I am paid a salary and I should not be paid extra money. However, allowances should be paid when health care providers travel out of their districts and provinces for work.

Who might make decisions around provision of allowances under VMMC programme?

The key decision would be to routinise male circumcision to be part of service delivery at health facility level. It is the campaign mode that tends to attract allowances for MC providers.

In terms of decision-making process, it will entail

- a) VMMC programme raising the issue of allowances to Technical Working Group (TWG)
- b) TWG will need to conduct an assessment of the issue
- c) TWG will make a recommendation to the Permanent Secretary for MoH
- d) Permanent Secretary MoH will draft a memo which will be adhered to by all health care providers.

How might you create demand for sustainable VMMC?

Creation of health promotions unit is key. A lot of communication, publicity and demand creation can be done. The social mobilisation team is key for demand creation. If we shifted our focus to infants (EIMC), the health promotions unit will need to come up with messages on the benefits of the same.

7) 1.Training

Curriculum modification for pre-service training of health care providers is key.

What might be the key decisions that need to take place on pre-service training of health care providers?

For Medical Doctors, there is already a component of VMMC in the curriculum. However, the curriculum for clinical officers and nurses will need to be modified.

What might be the decision-making process on pre-service training of health care providers?

- a) Need for discussions between Public Health and Clinical Care Department
- b) General Nursing Council (GNC) will need to change the curriculum for pre-service training of health care providers.
- c) Registrar of GNC will need to communicate with Permanent Secretary of MoH about the proposed modifications.
- d) Permanent Secretary will need to communicate the proposed modifications on pre-service training to Minister of Health
- e) Minister of Health will need to table the modifications before parliament

What might be the barriers in making decisions on pre-service training of health care providers?

The main barrier may be the mushrooming of different medical training institution as this may compromise or affect service delivery of quality health.

Who might be involved in the decision-making process on pre-service training of health care providers?

Health Professions Council of Zambia (HPCZ), GNC and Parliamentarians.

1. 1. Supply Chain

MoH is working with Medical Stores Limited in ensuring that commodities are bought. In the sustainable future, commodities can be bought by MSL.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on supply chain?

The main challenge will be funding to be the commodities.

1. 1. Indicators

What indicators might be measured in the sustainable future state where EIMC and EAMC is sustainable and integrated?

- a. Indicators are wide. We may need to capture the service points to see if the VMMC programme is on track. This will show us where most of the MC numbers are coming from whether its outreach or surgical wards.
- b. We may also want to track the numbers of MC providers in DHIS per health facility.

What new partnerships might we need to forge in the future state where EIMC and EAMC is sustainable and integrated?

We may need to continue with our current collaborating agencies that include Ministry of Education, Ministry of Gender, Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs, Ministry of Religious Affairs, Ministry of Community Development and Social Services and Ministry of Youth, Sport and Child Development.

How might you rate MoH's collaboration with each of these agencies?

Using a scale of 1 to 5 where 5 is very good and 1 is very poor, the collaboration can be said to be as follows:

- Ministry of Education: 4 out of 5
- Ministry of Gender: 1 out of 5
- Ministry of Religious Affairs: 1 out of 5
- Ministry of Chiefs and Traditional Affairs: 1 out of 5
- Ministry of Youth, Sport and Child Development: 2 out of 5

So far, collaboration with Ministry of Education has been very good.

What might be the barriers experienced on cross ministry collaboration?

The lack of directorates for health-related matters in other line ministries has affected continuity of discussions with MoH. The trend has been that different staff from line ministries attend meetings called by MoH and this affects continuity of discussions. Perhaps, the Permanent Secretary of MoH should request line ministries to appoint focal point persons on health matters.

What might motivate you (in your role) to move towards sustainability?

- a. Ownership of the VMMC programme and you feel proud of the achievements.
- b. It is for the benefit of people in general.
- c. There is need to move towards sustainability because of the impact of MC programme on reducing cervical cancer and HIV infections.

d. It is also the belief that I have in the VMMC programme and the results it has shown.

What are your greatest barriers?

- a. Convincing the general population that VMMC is good in view of the fact that some communities may not believe in male circumcision. This is where demand creation is required.
- b. Not being able to control the VMMC Programme because it is donor-driven.
- c. Gender dynamics. Some men do not feel comfortable to have a female MC provider and this may affect the VMMC programme.

WHO recently recommended restrictions on male circumcision for 10 – 14 young people due to adverse events observed among them. What are your thoughts?

If we exclude the 10 – 14 young people, then it stops being EAMC and that will impact the VMMC programme. MoH has been circumcising across the different age group and Zambia has not made any decisions regarding the declaration made by WHO.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Phone No: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Date: 13th xxxxxxx 2019

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

What is your role with regard to VMMC?

I am a xxx at Ministry of Health (MoH) xxxxxxx. My role entails xxxxxx commodities as well as xxxxxxx management with the help of the xxxxxxxx.

What might sustainability of VMMC mean to you?

Male circumcision (MC) started as a pilot in 2007. In 2009, it became a programme and since then, the supply chain system has been controlled by the implementation partners. This means that partners procure, store and distribute MC commodities. This means that Ministry of Health has no visibility in terms of commodities going to the health facilities. This situation where partners just buy commodities makes us to be worried of quality and conditions under which they are kept.

What is MoH's policy on supply chain?

As MoH we have advised implementation partners to have centralized system i.e. to move commodities to MSL. We would like the supply chain of VMMC programme be similar to the HIV or Malaria programme.

In terms of policy, it's up to the Technical Working Group (TWG) to move towards sustainability. Sustainability demands centrally managed supply chain system for MoH in order to supervise the procurement, storage and distribution of commodities. Without such a system, you end up having a situation where a given health facility has more stock than other health facilities. For us, we are at a level where we can make decisions. VITAD will be a good platform to make decisions. In 2013, we submitted an assessment report where we found a lot of gaps and we learnt some lessons. We need a robust system which will make coordination easy. If we can have all commodities in one place that will enhance visibility of MoH and standardized commodities will be guaranteed. This will also enhance ownership of the supply chain.

Every year, the VMMC programme has 3 campaigns and there are various challenges that are experienced such as:

- a) Lack of resources and commodities
- b) Lack of Transparency. CDC procures the commodities but MoH is not shown the books.
- c) Shortages of commodities arising from disjointed supply chain.

What decisions might be made in the sustainable future where Early Infant Male Circumcision (EIMC)/Early Adolescent Male Circumcision (EAMC) are integrated?

For HIV programme, all ARVs are stored by Medical Stores Limited. And we do not suffer shortages of ARVs. Firstly, Ministry of Health would need to make decisions around supply chain. The interest of MoH is not the money but to have centralized supply chain. We can have a situation where quantification and procurement are spearheaded by the implementation partners and product selection, storage and distribution can be handled by Ministry of Health through MSL. Secondly, Ministry of Health should communicate to the implementation partners about the need for centralized supply chain system.

Who might be the decision-making process on supply chain be?

- a) VMMC Programme works with the TWG. TWG would have to write to the Permanent Secretary of MoH.
- b) Permanent Secretary of Ministry of Health will have to study the proposal for centralized supply chain system.
- c) Once approval is granted, the Permanent Secretary of MoH will write to all implementation partners informing them of Government's decision on supply chain system.

This will enhance efficiency, accountability, transparency and will consequently reduce shortages of commodities.

Since the 2020 Operational Plan is being worked on, this is the best time to advocate for centralized supply chain system.

What might be the barriers in making decisions on supply chain?

- a) Inertia or resistance. Once the Permanent Secretary of MoH makes the decision, then it becomes policy.
- b) MSL has its own challenges which may be discouraging implementation partners. MSL has sufficient storage capacity for commodities. But the main challenge is with distribution of the commodities. The recommendation is that VMMC commodities should follow the distribution channel for the essential medicines kit.

Who might be better placed to make decisions on distribution of VMMC commodities?

The mandate of MSL is to receive, store and distribute commodities. However, the gap lies in commodities not being stored under MSL.

It is the Permanent Secretary of MoH and TWG to make the decisions. Implementation partners like CIDRZ procure commodities and store them. But CDC tend to allow provinces to procure commodities. This needs to be investigated why it is so.

Who at MoH should talk to CDC?

xxxxx. xxxxx issues during the national review meetings and TWG meetings. xxxxx need to engage the Permanent Secretary of MoH. xxxxx implementation partners that contracts and agreements were already signed and therefore it was not possible to go back to the donor and change the terms of agreement on supply chain. Perhaps, when new agreements are signed, consideration for centralized supply chain may be made.

Do you think the Permanent Secretary of MoH knows the problems with the supply Chain of VMMC?

Yes – Permanent Secretary is aware. xxxxx which was supposed to instruct implementation partners to move commodities to MSL but unfortunately, that letter was withdrawn and never sent. There is need for TWG to be transparent and uphold the decisions that are made.

How have MSL provincial hubs helped with commodities for VMMC programme?

MC commodities are front-loaded. Provinces do not have sufficient storage capacity. Therefore, the provincial hubs act as storage and health facilities and districts go and collect their commodities from the hubs.

What might motivate you (in your role) to move towards sustainability?

Ownership of the VMMC programme. We appreciate implementation partners. But the VMMC programme needs to mature and be sustainable. Supply chain is an important pillar of VMMC where we can easily be sustainable. The only problem is with the decision-making process.

What are your greatest barriers?

- a) CDC should make a decision on allocation of funds for supply chain. xxxx, and this has been done through the assessment report which highlighted the need for centralized supply chain. Perhaps, the VMMC Next should organise a meeting involving CDC, Permanent Secretary of Ministry of Health and TWG to discuss the supply chain agenda.
- b) Ministry of Health needs to document the policy directive on supply chain. The existing policy directive by MoH is centralized supply chain. The process should begin by reviewing the sustainability document and Permanent Secretary of MoH should adopt recommendations made in the sustainability documents which includes centralized supply chain.
- c) USAIDS and CDC will need to declare the financial budgets and commodities for VMMC programme. Implementation partners just share the numbers with MoH but do not share the costs associated to procurements of commodities. Perhaps, as we move towards sustainability, implementation partners may need to look for a neutral institution like Chemonics, to manage the supply chain system.

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email:

Phone No:

Date:

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxxx

POLICY

A “high Policy shift” is necessary. We need a “notch” in funding. World Bank is funding HIV, can we get a notch there? VMMC coordination officer would be necessary / to make the argument for a notch.

Barriers: Difficult to get to a clear % for what the notch ought to be. Notches need to be allocated against line items: Service Delivery, Supply Chain, Training. (But data doesn’t currently exist to indicate what these line items would be. There is no policy for them, necessarily. There is no data to show what they ought to be, in an integrated model.) (The sustainability roadmap indicates priority: 1. Training, 2. Supply, 3. Delivery). Other barriers include competition for scarce resources: Who’s most vocal? How can VMMC’s value be better framed so that it is perceived as a priority?

Motivators: We need better data from the local level to show impact evaluation and expected benefits (this is the language the donors speak).

Supply Chain funding changes need to happen in order that supply chain management changes can be enacted. (More about this in supply chain policy development).

FUNDING

We need to advocate for more centralized funding. We’re currently at 5%, we should shift that target to 25% by 2020. There are two components of this funding: Government grants and shifting donor funds, which currently go to IPs, to the ministry.

TRAINING

In-School communication should be constant... VMMC as preventative / demand generation should be embedded with School Health Services Platform (HIV education).

Currently not working very well with School Coordinators / Authorities. TWG list needs to be revised, we need to write to members, MoE, to partner.

There are ministry xxxxx: different objectives, bandwidth (“curriculum is already full”). We need to create downward pressure by embedding these programs in Strategic Plans.

Currently, EIMC is missing in policy. EAMC might not change much. The SBCC document needs to be changed to focus on EA/ EIMC. EIMC should be integrated with mid-wife training.

We need an unmet needs assessment. We need to find ways to add “sustainability” as a metric.

SUPPLY CHAIN

We need a phases approach for transitioning funding & management of supply chain. Right now Partners procure 100%. They stock 50%, MSL 50%. The ministry should be bringing that down, slowly. First to 30-70%, then fully.

Currently all IPs procure independently. We should implement a procurement shift, owned by MoH. Partners could pool their resources with MoH, then MoH procures for all. Issues with this: trust, control.

MoH can mitigate some of the resistance to this by identifying other funding sources, or diverting funding around partners. Equally, partners already pull resources from MSL for other programming. We could use those as benchmarks for making the argument.

We need a mandate for MSL to deliver. VMCM should be easily able to integrate with existing system.

How do we make this happen? PS needs to write to funders to begin diversion of procurement resources. A letter has already been written to PEPFAR. A document outlining the phased approach has already been created. This needs to be shared.

The donors, themselves, may mistrust the Gov't. ART & TB could be leveraged as benchmarks for dealing with mistrust (concerns: misuse, inefficiency)

Cross-Ministry collaboration programs need to be embedded in Strategic Plans. Indicators need to be integrated. Once it's in a policy document, it's relatively easy to implement.

High level advocates from PS office(s) across the ministries need to be organized, first. Their coordinators / directors can then inform HLA.

Decision Mapping Interview

Name: xxxxxxxx xxxxxxxx

Organisation: xxxxxxxxxx

Email:

Phone No:

Date:

Note-taker: xxxxxx xxxxxxx

FUNDING

#s for what “stable funding” means are under consideration. What is the minimum package? That hasn’t been answered yet. We don’t even have data on the current state of funding / expenditure. Some of the partners are outside of the system.

POLICY

The MoH needs to partner with IPs more rigorously to assess gaps in sustainability approach. We need to evaluate lessons learned from Adult VMMC.

A proposal is currently being considered to shift VMMC to nurses; there is a proposal cascade.

Routinization will require significant infrastructure changes. We’re redesigning/ building 108 facilities this year. They will become the blueprint for the future.

SERVICE DELIVERY

There is an historical bias towards outreach programs due to the structure of existing programming. There will always need to be a mix of static + outreach, but available staff might not be able to maintain outreach in an integrated future.

RE: Cross Ministry

We should be thinking “intersectoral” not necessarily “inter-ministry.” Specific groups will need to address key determinants. This starts at National, then Provincial (following the Chiefs), then districts.

Dr. NAYANA Network Plan Site Grid 2031 : 20,000 Health care workers PUBLIC HEALTH - WORKING CLOSE LEVERAGING OTHER PROGRAMS : PRIMARYLY HIV FEDERAL CHIEFS

Decision Mapping Framework : STATE x OBJECTIVE

	Policy	Funding	Service Delivery	Training	Supply Chain	Indicators	Cross-Ministry Collaboration
Future State(s) Sustainable BMC / BMC	Policy direction on integrating VMMC in reproductive health package	Alternative funding and allocation strategies	Transitioning standalone clinics into integrated medical clinics in hospitals and outpatient departments at health centres	Curriculum modification for Pre-service training of health care workers	Centrally managed supply chain system for all commodities	National service indicators in the national health information management systems	Connections, interactions and mutual support between health and education systems in ways that would integrate health education, demand generation and service provision for adolescent youth in primary and secondary schools
	Copy/ paste DECISION. Addresses gaps of teams while preserving privacy & quality. maximize EA/CI footprint.	Fund source unclear - identify secondary sources to ensure funding	Static facilities - IT'S A MATTER OF PRIORITIZING X COST		• DONORS TO FUNDING SUPPLY CHAIN DIRECTLY • CENTRALLY MANAGED STOCKS • STATES HAVE THEIR OWN FUNDING. (to help individual centers)		
Transitional State(s)	- Policy addressing team structure - should be legislation. - Policy decision how to address EA. MULTIPLE STAKEHOLDERS IN CONFLICT. ENDS WHO TO HAVE THE EVOLVING.	- Shift from PRACTICE SUPPORT - SUSTAINING SINGLE FUNDING IS STILL BEING CONSIDERED / STUDIED - WHO IS THE MAIN FUNDING PACKAGE? - INCREASE SCHEMATIC	- Shift from PRACTICE SUPPORT	WE NEED TO RE-EVALUATE OUR TRAINING, UNIVERSITY - Important issue of education - BACKUP BETTER (longer term use)	- SHIFTING PRACTICES THAT ARE FUNDING THE SUPPLY CHAIN - CENTRAL MANAGEMENT IS JUST ABOUT THE COSTS	- Transition to HUIS IS HAPPENING ... BUT SLOWLY - And BMC/CI IS NOT COMPLETE, UNDERSTANDING OF WORKLOADS NOT COMPLETE - NOT SOMEONE IS RESPONSIBLE REVERSE OSMOSIS IS AN OUTLIER	Prevention & Promotion TO BE ENHANCED.
Current State Benchmark Programs		- Difficulty retaining Primary health care workers - Some practices outside the system	MIXED DMA BETWEEN OUTREACH vs. STATIC.	A lot of OUTREACH SUPPLEMENT TRAINING ... CONFUSION, ... UNCOORDINATED FOCUS OF PRE-SERVICE			- CASE ILLNESS IS ALREADY HAPPENING, BUT DIVERGENCE OCCURS ② OPERATIONAL

